

DEVELOPING B1-LEVEL LEARNERS' DIALOGIC SPEAKING SKILLS THROUGH THE USE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

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Abstract. In language learning, speaking is often considered one of the most difficult skills, especially for intermediate learners. Many B1-level students have problems when they try to express their ideas clearly or continue a conversation. Sometimes they know the grammar, but they cannot use it in real communication. This paper looks at how artificial intelligence (AI) can help improve dialogic speaking skills. Today, AI tools are becoming more common in education and give learners more opportunities to practice speaking in a simple and less stressful way. In my opinion, such tools help students feel more confident and active. The paper discusses the importance of speaking, the role of interaction, and the use of AI in language learning. The results show that regular practice with AI can improve learners' fluency and confidence.

Keywords: speaking skill, dialogic speech, B1 learners, artificial intelligence, communication.

Annotatsiya. Til o'rganishda gapirish ko'nikmasi, ayniqsa, o'rta darajadagi o'quvchilar uchun eng qiyin ko'nikmalardan biri hisoblanadi. Ko'pgina B1 darajasidagi talabalar o'z fikrlarini aniq ifodalashda yoki suhbatni davom ettirishda qiyinchiliklarga duch kelishadi. Ba'zan ular grammatikani bilsalar-da, undan real muloqotda foydalana olmaydilar. Ushbu ishda dialogik nutq ko'nikmalarini takomillashtirishda sun'iy intellektning (AI) qanday yordam berishi ko'rib chiqiladi. Bugungi kunda sun'iy intellekt vositalari ta'limda tobora keng tarqalmoqda va o'quvchilarga oddiy hamda kamroq stressli muhitda gapirishni mashq qilish uchun ko'proq imkoniyatlar yaratmoqda. Mening fikrimcha, bunday vositalar talabalarga o'zlariga bo'lgan ishonchni oshirishga va faolroq bo'lishga yordam beradi. Maqolada gapirishning ahamiyati, o'zaro muloqotning o'rni va til o'rganishda sun'iy intellektdan foydalanish masalalari muhokama qilinadi. Natijalar shuni ko'rsatadiki, sun'iy intellekt bilan muntazam mashq qilish o'quvchilarning nutq ravonligi va o'ziga bo'lgan ishonchini oshirishi mumkin.

Tayanch so'zlar: gapirish ko'nikmasi, dialogik nutq, B1 darajasidagi o'quvchilar, sun'iy intellekt, muloqot.

Аннотация. В изучении языка говорение часто считается одним из самых сложных навыков, особенно для учащихся среднего уровня. Многие студенты уровня B1 сталкиваются с проблемами, когда пытаются четко выразить свои мысли или поддержать беседу. Иногда они знают грамматику, но не могут использовать её в реальном общении. В данной работе рассматривается, как искусственный интеллект (ИИ) может помочь в улучшении навыков диалогической речи. Сегодня инструменты ИИ становятся всё более распространёнными в образовании и дают учащимся больше возможностей

практиковать речь простым и менее стрессовым способом. По моему мнению, такие инструменты помогают студентам чувствовать себя более уверенными и активными. В статье обсуждаются важность говорения, роль взаимодействия и использование ИИ в изучении языка. Результаты показывают, что регулярная практика с ИИ может улучшить беглость речи и уверенность учащихся.

Ключевые слова: навык говорения, диалогическая речь, учащиеся уровня B1, искусственный интеллект, коммуникация.

Introduction

Today, learning a foreign language is not only about grammar rules or vocabulary lists. It is more about being able to communicate with other people in real life. Among all language skills, speaking is one of the most important, but at the same time, it is one of the hardest to develop (Brown, 2001). I have noticed that many B1-level learners feel nervous when they try to speak. They often stop in the middle of a sentence because they do not know what to say next or they are afraid of making mistakes.

Dialogic speaking is especially important because it reflects real communication. In real life, people do not speak alone — they communicate with others, ask questions, give answers, and share opinions. This makes speaking more challenging, because learners need to think quickly and react during the conversation (Richards, 2008).

From my experience, traditional classroom activities are sometimes not enough. Students do not always have enough time to practice speaking, and some of them feel shy in front of others. Because of this, new technologies like artificial intelligence are becoming very useful. AI tools, such as chatbots, allow learners to practice speaking anytime they want. They can repeat, make mistakes, and try again without feeling embarrassed (Holmes et al., 2019).

This paper aims to show how artificial intelligence can help B1-level learners improve their dialogic speaking skills and become more confident in communication.

Theoretical Background

Speaking is a productive skill, which means that learners need to actively use language, not just understand it. To speak well, learners should develop several important aspects. These include fluency, accuracy, pronunciation, and interaction (Brown, 2001).

Fluency means speaking without too many pauses. Many learners at B1 level struggle with this because they spend too much time thinking about grammar. Accuracy is also important, as learners should try to use correct grammar and vocabulary. However, it is normal to make mistakes during the learning process (Harmer, 2007).

Pronunciation is another important part of speaking. If pronunciation is not clear, communication can become difficult. At the same time, learners need to develop interactional skills. This includes asking questions, responding to others, and keeping the conversation going.

There are two main types of speaking: monologic and dialogic. Monologic speaking is when one person speaks for a longer time, for example, during a presentation. Dialogic speaking, on the other hand, involves communication between two or more people. In my opinion, dialogic speaking is more important for everyday communication, especially for B1 learners (Richards, 2008).

Artificial intelligence is becoming more popular in education. In language learning, AI tools can create situations that are similar to real conversations. For

example, chatbots can ask questions, give responses, and help learners practice speaking step by step.

One of the biggest advantages of AI is that learners can practice anytime and as much as they want (Luckin et al., 2016).

Methodology

This study focuses on B1-level learners who often have difficulties in speaking. Many of them have limited vocabulary, make grammatical mistakes, and feel unsure when they speak. To help them improve, AI-based speaking activities were used.

Learners practiced speaking with the help of AI tools, especially chatbots. These tools allowed them to take part in simple conversations, answer questions, and practice everyday situations. For example, learners practiced dialogues such as ordering food, asking for directions, or talking about their daily routine.

Different types of activities were used, including role-plays, question-and-answer tasks, and short conversations. These activities were designed to make learners speak more and feel more comfortable.

To check the progress, several criteria were used. These included fluency, accuracy, pronunciation, and interaction. Learners were observed before and after using AI tools. Their speaking performance was compared to see if there were any improvements (Holmes et al., 2019).

Results and Discussion

The results showed that AI tools had a positive effect on learners' speaking skills. After some time, students became more confident and were able to speak more freely. They did not stop as often as before and could continue conversations more easily.

Another improvement was seen in vocabulary use. Learners started using more words and expressions during speaking. Their grammar also improved, although some mistakes were still present, which is normal at this level (Harmer, 2007).

One important point was motivation. Many students enjoyed using AI tools because they felt less pressure. In a traditional classroom, some learners are afraid of making mistakes in front of others. However, when they practiced with AI, they felt more relaxed and were willing to try more.

It was also noticed that learners became better at responding during conversations. They learned how to react faster and keep the dialogue going. This is an important part of dialogic speaking (Richards, 2008).

At the same time, it is important to say that AI should not fully replace teachers. Teachers still play an important role in guiding learners and explaining difficult points. The best results can be achieved when AI is used together with traditional teaching methods.

Conclusion

In conclusion, speaking is a very important skill in learning a foreign language, especially at the B1 level. Many learners find it difficult to speak confidently and take part in conversations. Developing dialogic speaking skills is necessary for real communication.

This paper shows that artificial intelligence can be a useful tool in improving speaking skills. AI provides learners with more opportunities to practice, helps them feel more confident, and supports their learning process.

In my opinion, combining traditional teaching methods with modern technologies like AI can give the best results. Teachers should try to include such tools in their lessons to help students become more active and confident speakers.

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